

“IVANHOE” AS A SIGNIFICANT NOVEL OF ENGLISH LITERATURE

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Annotation: The article examines one of the well-known works of Walter Scott, the reasons for reading the novel, the Saxons and Normans, the image of the main hero, Ivanhoe and his best qualities.

Key words: *genre, novel, The Scottish, Saxons, Normans, author's image, author's origin, history, Ivanhoe.*

There are numerous genres in literature which differ from each other, according to their usage and one of them is novel genre. The study of the novel as a genre is recognizable as this genre is loved and estimated highly by thousands of people. However, novel is unique as well as being only emerging and still unfinished genre. The birth and formation of the novel genre go back to the past and in its history discovered a plethora of talented novelists with bestsellers works of theirs. Moreover, novels can be various according to the aims, which they hold. One of them historical novels with the help of what one can imagine and be aware of the past people, events, atmosphere and others. History itself (and therefore historical fiction) possesses interest for us more as the **unfolding of certain moral and mental developments** than as the mere enumeration of facts. Historical fiction offers an “**analysis of recognizable human character** within a specific set of circumstances”, that’s to say, we can re-experience the social and human motives which led us to think, feel and how people did in historical reality in addition to developing an **awareness that the events of history have an impact**

on the contemporary [1.Grindon Leger “Studies in the historical fiction film.” Temple University Press, 2010].

Furthermore, by reading historical fictions one induces empathy and a **live connection between then and now** what’s more, the historical novel allows us **to contemplate social change**. We see in change hindsight, which then allows the individual to reflect upon their contemporary circumstance. Similarly, historical fiction can trace the path of religious and political change. Thus, people are really into reading historical fictions and there are a series of irreplicable, bestseller works which keep valuable information about the history of this or that country and still are read with great enthusiasm.

“Ivanhoe” by Walter Scott is one of the most famous historical work which is read, liked by many people and still in use. Walter Scott is a famous Scottish writer who wrote the famous adventure novel “Ivanhoe”, which became the most popular novel in the world.[2.Ivanhoe" in Blackwood's Edinburgh Magazine, No. 33, December, 1819, pp.262-72].

His works contain a vivid combination of the fantastic and the real, which is impossible not to notice while reading the work. The author always tried to more clearly demonstrate the moral values of his characters, to reflect the then life and customs of the English people and was able to combine historical truth with artistic fiction [3.Shaw Harry E. The Forms of Historical Fiction: Sir Walter Scott and His Successors. Ithaca,Cornell University Press,1983].

The best work of his artistic work of all time is considered “Ivanhoe”, where the main character is an ideal knight. This is the first novel in which Walter Scott tried a **specifically English topic**.

However, it should be noted that even within the pretense of giving a historical character to the work, the author himself acknowledges that he has taken certain **liberties** in that sense (mixture of fictional and historical characters. Walter Scott manages to awaken with this work the **public fondness for the historical literary genre** in which his fantasy uses the resources of scholarly

research, complementing it with his talents as a storyteller. **It manages to reflect the historical reality faithfully despite telling an imaginary story, but very well framed and linked**, so that its plausibility is palpable. It is obvious that the work shows the enmity between Saxons and Normans at the time in question, as well as other environmental details [4.Millgate Jane.Walter Scott:The Making of the Novelist Edinburgh, 1984].

This does not diminish the importance of the novel, but rather Walter **Scott's narrative agility ensures reader interest.** *Ivanhoe* is a rather sharp-edged story of intolerance, both personal and social, in the Middle Ages. Furthermore, the main character of the work, Ivanhoe can really be considered a knight who symbolizes courage, bravery and idealism in everything. Therefore, it is believed that the Ivanhoe knight, the main character of Walter Scott's adventure novel, should be considered ideal, because he absorbed the characteristics of a person from whom an example should be taken.

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